

BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA IJODIY FAOLIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA OID ISHLARI TAHLILI.

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Annotatsiya. Tadqiqotning faoliyat doirasida amalga oshirilgan tajriba-sinov ishlari pedagogik faoliyatni ijodiy tashkil etish, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijod, ijod qilish samaradorligini, amallarni bajarishda diqqatni va fikrni jamlashni shakllantirish asosida turli shakl, metod va vositalar yordamida shakllantirishga oid bilim, ko'nikma va malakalar hamda ijod faoliyatni shakllantirishga yordam berishini tasdiqladi.

Kalit so'z: ijod, rivojlanish, boshlang'ich sinf, tahlil.

ANALYSIS OF WORK ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

Abstract. The experimental work carried out in the framework of the research was based on the creative organization of pedagogical activities, the formation of creativity, efficiency of creation in elementary school students, concentration of attention and thought in the performance of actions, using various forms, methods and tools and confirmed that skills and creativity help to shape activities.

Key word: creativity, development, primary class, analysis.

АНАЛИЗ РАБОТЫ ПО РАЗВИТИЮ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ МЛАДШИХ КЛАССОВ.

Аннотация. Экспериментальная работа, проведенная в рамках исследования, была основана на творческой организации педагогической деятельности, формировании творческих способностей, продуктивности творчества у учащихся младших классов, концентрации внимания и мысли при выполнении действий с использованием различных форм, методов. и инструменты и подтвердили, что навыки и творческий подход помогают формировать деятельность.

Ключевые слова: творчество, развитие, начальный класс, анализ.

Olib borilgan xar qanday ilmiy tadqiqot ishining ilmiy yangiligi doirasida olib borilgan tajriba-sinov ishlarining natijalariga bevosita bog'liq hisoblanadi. Agar tadqiqot ishining gipotezasi tajriba sinovda o'z tasdig'ini topsa, ilgari surilgan yangi metodika va texnologiya orqali mavjud holat ijobiy tomonga o'zgarishi, pedagogik jarayonning samaradorligi oshishi zarur. Dissertatsiyani nazariy bobini asoslash va uni amaliyotda qo'llash, tajriba-sinovdan o'tkazish tadqiqot ishining muhim bosqichini tashkil qiladi.

Tadqiqotning faoliyat doirasida amalga oshirilgan tajriba-sinov ishlari pedagogik faoliyatni ijodiy tashkil etish, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijod, ijod qilish samaradorligini, amallarni bajarishda diqqatni va fikrni jamlashni shakllantirish asosida turli shakl, metod va vositalar yordamida shakllantirishga oid bilim, ko'nikma va malakalar hamda ijod faoliyatni shakllantirishga yordam berishini tasdiqladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari bilim va ko'nikmalarini miqdoriy solishtirish natijalari, tajriba va nazorat guruhlarida bilish faoliyatiga yo'naltirilganlik darajasi tadqiqot ishiga doir maxsus tayyorlangan savolnomalar asosida aniqlandi. Mazkur savolnoma orqali boshlang'ich sinf

o'quvchilarining bilish faoliyatni rivojlantirishning pedagogik tizimining mavjud holati aniqlangan edi. Tajriba guruhida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirishga oid turli metodlardan foydalanildi va u uch bosqichda amalga oshirilgan tajriba-sinov ishlarining natijalari bo'yicha samaradorlik aniqlandi. Samaradorlikni aniqlash quyidagi yo'nalishlar bo'yicha olib borildi:

- aynan texnologiya amallarni, mashqlarni o'rganish bo'yicha;
- aynan texnologiyaga oid ko'nikma va malaka, kompetensiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha;
- boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni shakllantirish bo'yicha;
- boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'quv muhiti bo'yicha va h.k.

Bu qayd etilgan yo'nalishlar bo'yicha taqqoslash va umumlashtirishlardan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqot doirasida tajriba ishlarining birinchi bosqichi (2017-2018) ta'kidlovchi tajriba-sinov ishlaridan iborat bo'lib, uning asosiy maqsadi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish va fikrlarini o'stirishning ta'lim amaliyotidagi holatini o'rganish va mavjud muammolarni aniqlashdan iborat. Tajriba-sinov ishlari maqsadidan kelib chiqqan holda quyidagi vazifalar belgilandi va amalga oshirildi:

1-4 sinf o'quvchilari uchun texnologiya darsligi va manbalari o'rganildi va tahlil qilindi; boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish uchun o'qituvchilarining kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarlik darajalarining holati aniqlandi;

so'rovnoma va test savollari yordamida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatiga oid dastlabki bilim, ko'nikma, malakalari tizimi o'rganildi;

uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida o'quvchilarning bilish faoliyatni yo'lga qo'yish, bilim olish istagini o'stirish, fikrlarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha olib borilayotgan o'quv-tarbiyaviy ishlar jarayoni bilan tanishildi.

Ta'kidlovchi tajriba-sinov ishlari natijalarini ilmiy-nazariy tahlil qilish jarayonida quyidagilarga asosiy e'tibor qaratildi:

1. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish, texnologiyadan fikrlarini oshirish bo'yicha D T S, o'quv dasturi, darsliklar va qo'llanmalarining yutuq va kamchiliklari tahlil qilindi va aniqlandi.

2. Pedagoglarning boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faolligini oshirish xamda rivojlantirish haqidagi fikrlarini umumlashtirish maqsadida so'rovnoma javoblari tahlil qilindi va umumlashtirildi.

3. Amaliy ishlari jarayonida yo'l qo'yilgan kamchiliklar aniqlandi va bartaraf etish choralarini ishlab chiqildi.

Yuqoridagilar asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish, texnologiya ta'limiga oid bilimlarini o'stirish, mantiqiy va tahliliy fikrlarini rivojlantirishning mavjud holati va uni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari aniqlandi. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida bilish faoliyatni rivojlantirishga oid tushunchalar, ko'nikma va malakalarini talab darajasida rivojlantirish jarayonining mazmuni, shakl va metodlari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar to'plandi.

Olingan natijalar umumlashtirildi, xulosalar chiqarildi va muammo doirasida doimiy monitoring o'rnatildi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari o'rtasida texnologiyaga oid bilimlarini, u asosida ijodiy faolligini rivojlantirish doirasida olib borilgan anketa so'rovlari shuni ko'rsatdiki, ular

boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida texnologiya ta'limi doirasida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish asosan nostandart topshiriqlarni bajarishda samarali amalga oshirilishini ta'kidlashdi. Bu borada musobaqalar, maktablarda o'tkaziladigan bilimlar bellashuvining ahamiyatini yuqori baholashdi. Bundan ko'rinadiki, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining amaliyot bilan bog'lanishiga muhim e'tibor qaratish maqsadga muvofiq.

Shakllantiruvchi tajriba-sinov ishlarini o'tkazish jarayonida hamkorlikda o'qitish, davra suhbatlari, muz yorar, kichik guruhlarda ishlash o'yin, sahna ko'rinishi, kommunikativ-suhbat texnologiyasi kabi ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanildi.

Yakunlovchi tajriba-sinov ishlari ushbu jarayondagi oxirgi va muhim bosqich bo'lganligi bois unga alohida e'tibor qaratildi. Bu bosqichda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida texnologiyani o'qitish asosida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan nazariya, mazmun hamda uni amalga oshirish metodikasining yutuq va kamchiliklarini aniqlash, takomillashtirish hamda samaradorlik darajasini xolisona baholash asosiy maqsad qilib olindi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirishga doir tajriba ishlarining amaliy tatbiqi ularning faoliyatiga ikki xil yondashish lozimligini taqozo etdi:

1. Sinf va barcha o'quvchilar uchun bir xil yondashish;
2. Iqtidorli o'quvchilarning fikrlash tarzini, ijodiy faoliyatni hisobga olgan holda yakkama-yakka, alohida yondashib o'qitish.

Pedagogik didaktik andozaning tashkiliy-pedagogik shartlar faoliyati uchun ko'p tarmoqli asoslari ishlab chiqilgan:

- o'qitish asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni arifmetik bilimi va ijodiy faoliyatni didaktik sintezini ta'minlovchi sharoit yaratish;
- maktab ta'limida bilish faoliyatni aks ettiruvchi tizimni shakllantirish;

Pedagogik tajriba-sinov ishlarini tashkil etish va o'tkazish jarayonida umumiy maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun quyidagilar bajarildi:

1. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida va o'qituvchilarda fikrlash, tanqidiy tafakkur qilishning mavjud holatini o'rganish. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarni va o'qituvchilari o'rtasida anketa so'rovlarini o'tkazish, suhbatlar, muloqotlar tashkil etish, to'garak jarayonini kuzatish, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish bo'yicha pedagogik kuzatishlar olib borish, ta'lim mazmunining mavjud holatiga nisbatan o'qituvchilarni fikr-mulohazalarini o'rganish va tahlil etish kabi holatlar mazkur vazifani samarali hal etish uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qildi.

2. Texnologiyani o'qitish asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faolligini oshirish, texnologik bilim olishga, teran fikrlashga o'rgatish imkonini beruvchi shart-sharoitlarni aniqlash. Vazifani ijobiy hal etish jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini ijodiy faoliyatni shakllantirishga yordam beruvchi umumiy omillar aniqlandi, rivojlantirish mexanizmi yaratildi, texnologiyabo'yicha Davlat ta'lim standartlarida belgilangan o'quvchilar egallashi lozim bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma, malakalar va kompetensiyalar hajmi, mazmuni aniqlandi.

3. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida texnologiyani o'qitish asosida ijodiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish jarayonida ko'zga tashlanayotgan muammolarni aniqlash hamda ularni bartaraf etish chora-tadbirlarini belgilash. Mazkur vazifaning amalga oshirilishi boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari

va o'qituvchilari bilan bevosita muloqot, suhbat hamda bahs-munozaralar, o'zaro tajriba almashish asosida amalga oshirildi.

4. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida texnologiyani o'qitish asosida bilish faoliyatni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi samarador ta'lim texnologiyalarini belgilash. Ana shu maqsadga yo'naltirilgan faoliyat ta'lim jarayonida fikrlarini rivojlantirishga va ijodiy faoliyatga asoslangan ishlanmalarni, metodik tavsiyalarni, ko'rgazmali materiallarni yaratish, o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyati natijalarini tahlil etish, ularda hosil bo'lgan ijodiy faoliyati darajasini aniqlash, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatida ishtirok etish ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil etish asosida amalga oshirildi.

5. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida texnologiyani o'qitish asosida ijodiy faoliyatni shakllanganlik darajasini aniqlovchi baholash mezonlarini ishlab chiqish. Mezonlar tadqiqot ishida ilgari surilgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida bilish faoliyatning tarkibiy qismlariga muvofiq ishlab chiqildi.

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